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Case Report

Platelet Rich Plasma: A new treatment option for a Morel-Lavallee lesion

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Abstract:	<p>Background: A Morel-Lavallee Lesion (ML lesion) is an internal degloving injury, associated with blunt trauma or shearing injuries. Resulting in a separation of soft tissue and muscle from the underlying fascia and disrupt perforating blood vessels creating a potential fluid filled space with blood, lymph and necrotic fat, leading to potential bacterial colonization leading to infection and chronically, can develop a fibrous capsule that can affect muscle mass and develop muscle weakness.</p> <p>Purpose: To provide a new treatment option and a review of our clinical treatment and management of ML lesion injuries that have occurred to US Army Soldiers.</p> <p>Results: Complete resolution of the Morel-Lavallee lesion with weekly injections of Platelet Rich Plasma (PRP) x four weeks in conjunction with hematoma aspiration along with traditional soft tissue compression, cryotherapy and physical therapy with a return to base line physical activity.</p> <p>Conclusion: PRP injections into the hematoma and adjacent injured soft tissue can assist the healing process and resolution of a ML lesion</p> <p>Keywords: Morel-Lavallee Lesion, Platelet Rich Plasma, Degloving injury, PRP injections</p>

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Case report

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12 Ann B Lebeck, MD
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15 Abstract

16 Background: A Morel-Lavallee Lesion (ML lesion) is an internal degloving injury, associated with
17 blunt trauma or shearing injuries. Resulting in a separation of soft tissue and muscle from the
18 underlying fascia and disrupt perforating blood vessels creating a potential fluid filled space
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4 Introduction
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7 Sports Medicine is a key resource within the US Army, treating acute and chronic injuries of
8 active duty soldiers. The soldiers are evaluated and treated similarly as an elite athlete, but
9 with a unique challenge. The US Army soldier is not a seasonal athlete but is in a 'year round
10 sport' and musculoskeletal injuries can pose a problem for army readiness.
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13 Our clinic performs Platelet Rich Plasma (PRP) injections using autologous concentrated
14 platelets (ACP) to treat and assist in the healing and resolution of acute and chronic
15 musculoskeletal injuries. This is our first case of treating a ML lesion with PRP injections.
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19 The Morel- Lavallee Lesion (ML lesion) is a shearing soft tissue injury first described in 1853 by
20 French Physician Maurice Morel-Lavallee.
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22 ML lesions occur as a result of a degloving injury in which the skin, subcutaneous and even
23 muscle tissue are separated from the underlying fascia, disrupting the perforating vessels. The
24 newly created space can fill with blood, lymph and necrotic fat potentially leading to bacterial
25 colonization and infections and muscle weakness.
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29 Non-surgical treatments for ML lesions have included compression bandaging, percutaneous
30 drainage, irrigation and suction drainage, liposuction, cryotherapy and in some cases of
31 recalcitrant fluid collections sclerodesis injections of talc, bleomycin and alcohol.
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37 Platelet Rich Plasma
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40 Platelet Rich Plasma (PRP) is a concentrate of platelet rich plasma proteins derived from whole
41 blood, and then centrifuged to remove the red blood cells. It has a greater concentration of
42 growth factors than whole blood and is used to encourage a brisk healing response.
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44 Autologous conditioned plasma (ACP) is an autologous blood plasma that is naturally occurring
45 in the body that is conditioned as part of a special production process, which is separated from
46 the other blood components and concentrated.
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49 ACP is a form of platelet rich plasma. PRP is a general term for a type of plasma that contains a
50 high concentration of thrombocytes that is separated from whole blood usually by
51 centrifugation. ACP includes thrombocytes and several growth factors including TGF-beta,
52 PDGF (platelet derived growth factor), EGF (endothelial growth factor) VEGF (vascular
53 endothelial growth factor, FGF (fibroblast growth factor and IGF (insulin growth factor).
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58 These growth factors perform a variety of tasks including regulation of cellular migration and
59 proliferation, stimulation of cell replication, stimulation of angiogenesis and acceleration of
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4 mesenchymal stem cell replication and osteoid production released from the platelets, inducing
5 a healing response and allowing cellular repair and improvement in pain and function
6 associated with fibrotic scar tissue seen in muscle and tendon acute and chronic injury.
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10 11 Discussion

12 A 49 year old Caucasian male with a history of left ACL injury and repair and subsequent left
13 knee osteoarthritis, presented to our Sports Medicine clinic four days after a shearing injury to
14 the left medial thigh. Injury was a result of a fall while standing inside the truck bed of a F-350
15 truck. He lost his footing and fell to the ground with his entire inner thigh coming into contact
16 with the tail gate.
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18 He was evaluated in the Urgent Care on the day of injury due to left thigh swelling and bruising
19 and inability to fully extend his left knee.
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24 Baseline functional activities prior to injury were bicycling, walking and bowling.
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28 Clinical exam findings: oval shaped dark purple hematoma with fluctuance (measuring
29 approximately 10 cm x 6 cm) and induration along the medial aspect of his left distal inner thigh
30 with extension to below the medial knee joint line and a guarded full knee extension due to
31 pain and soft tissue swelling along the distal inner thigh and extending across the joint line and
32 decreased quad firing. Ultrasound imaging confirmed fluid accumulation in the soft tissue
33 layers without a joint effusion. Aspiration of the hematoma was performed followed by
34 compression along this region at his initial visit.
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40 MRI of the left knee and femur confirmed intact ACL graft, with tricompartmental osteoarthritis
41 and fluid collection in the subcutaneous tissue of the medial knee above the knee joint (*6.3 cm*
42 *AP x 1.8 cm TRV x 9 cm AP*).
43

44 Treatment plan included: 4 weekly visits, for ultrasound guided aspiration of the soft tissue
45 hematoma followed by PRP injections directly into the hematoma and into the soft tissue and
46 areas of induration and the medial distal 1/3rd of the femur to include the distal adductor and
47 extensor tendons, medial collateral ligament and surrounding soft tissue using a peppering
48 technique, totaling 10-12 mls of PRP at each visit. (Negative fluid culture obtained on Week#2).
49

50 Modalities included: cryotherapy, compression thigh sleeve.
51

52 Follow up visits: Quad firing returned on week#2, no further hematoma formation but a small
53 area of induration adjacent to proximal medial trochlea that was treated with soft tissue
54 massage. As part of his treatment plan for his underlying left knee tricompartmental
55 osteoarthritis he underwent ultrasound guided Intra-articular injections to the left knee with
56 Hyaluronic Acid x five weeks and on week #5 PRP(5 ml's) was injected intra-articularly with an
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4 additional 5 ml's of PRP to the external soft tissue structures of the medial aspect of the knee to
5 include: the distal vastus medialis muscle and tendon, and medial patella femoral ligament,
6 medial collateral ligament and soft tissue of the medial thigh, noted on ultrasound to have
7 hyperechoic signaling in these structures and palpable tenderness correlating to the ultrasound
8 findings. Patient did have a history of chronic left knee pain and reported a decrease in joint
9 pain and increased quad strength and felt confident to initiate a jog/running program 2 weeks
10 post injections, improving his base line functional level.
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16 Morel Lavallee lesions can occur with any shearing blow or blunt trauma disrupting the soft
17 tissue and muscle from the underlying fascia and a high clinical suspicion is required for a ML
18 lesion when evaluating an injury that is associated with blunt trauma with a hematoma. PRP is
19 a treatment option adjunct to hematoma aspiration when addressing soft tissue, ligament and
20 tendon injury which can decrease likelihood of developing chronic conditions such as
21 tendinosis, fibrotic scar tissue.
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